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THE EXISTING INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT IN THE CONSTRUCTION SECTOR OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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СУЩЕСТВУЮЩИЙ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННЫЙ КЛИМАТ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНОМ СЕКТОРЕ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

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O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI QURILISH SOHASIDA MAVJUD INVESTITSIYA MUHITI

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abstract

This article provides analytical information on the reforms carried out in the field of investments in the Republic of Uzbekistan, foreign, direct investments involved in the fields, as well as analytical information on investments involved in the construction sector, as well as author's proposals.

аннотация

В данной статье приведены аналитические данные о проводимых в Республике Узбекистан реформах в сфере инвестиций, привлечении иностранных, прямых инвестиций в отрасли, в том числе в строительную отрасль, а также предложения авторов.

annotatsiya

Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida investitsiyalar sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar, sohalarga jalb qilinayotgan xorijiy, to'g'ridan-to'g'ri investitsiyalar shu qatorda qurilish

sohasiga jalb qilinayotgan investitsiyalar yuzasidan tahliliy ma'lumotlar hamda muallif takliflari keltirib o'tilgan.

Keywords:

foreign investment, construction, investment environment

Ключевые слова:

иностранные инвестиции, строительство, инвестиционная среда.

Kalit so'zlar:

xorijiy investitsiyalar, qurilish, investitsiya muhiti.

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Introduction

The whole world is characterized by the main directions of attracting new technologies to the economy at any time, attracting investments in industries, modernizing the economy. For this reason, it is necessary to attract Comprehensive Capital in the tourism sector of the country, in the socio-economic sphere, in the construction sector, which is divided from the main directions. Our country has also created an investment environment that meets the requirements of the world community. The government has provided all the facilities for investors. Therefore, the third direction of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan, a program for the comprehensive development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, was also aimed at this area, focusing on creating wide opportunities for the construction of the state and society.

Analysis and results

In January 2023, a total of Rs. in January 2022, in the cross section of the regions, in particular, the city of Tashkent (1721.7 billion USD) was completed. sum), Tashkent region (480.0 crore. Soum) and Fergana region (344.5 billion sum) high volume of construction work was noted. The distribution of construction work performed in the Republic of Uzbekistan in January 2023 by types of economic activities is as follows:

- the direction of construction of buildings and structures amounted to 67.1% share, compared with the corresponding period of 2022 - 66.5 %;
- the direction of construction of civil facilities accounted for a 19.9% share and amounted to 70.9% compared with the corresponding period of 2022;
- the direction of specialized construction work accounted for a 13.0% share and 56.1% compared to the corresponding period of 2022.

A large part of the completed construction work concerns the construction of new buildings and structures. 65.8% of total construction work or 3,296.7 billion. sum construction works are aimed precisely at creating new production facilities, residential and other social facilities in the economy. 302.7 billion from new construction by major construction organizations. sum works were completed or the share of the total large construction organizations in new construction works was 9.2%. 1,988.6 billion at the expense of new construction on small enterprises and microfirms. the share of soums or total small enterprises and microfirms in new construction work was 60.3%. The informal sector contribution in the volume of new construction works was 1,005.4 billion. the share of the sum or their sum was 30.5%. From the above figures we can

also see that from year to year we can conclude that the good of the investment environment in our country and the income of the population has increased to create the economic basis for correctly determining the regulation, direction and distribution of investment processes in the conditions of modernization of the economy, ensuring the conditions that make it possible. It was observed that the volume of construction work performed by small enterprises and microfirms increased sharply in the current period compared to other organizations that performed construction work.

*Figure 1. Construction works
(growth rate, %)*

Territories	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Republic of Uzbekistan	107,2	106,0	114,3	122,9	109,5	106,8	106,6
Republic of Karakalpakstan	89,4	112,3	125,8	128,0	107,0	103,8	107,3
Andijan	106,4	103,1	121,8	99,3	109,5	108,7	109,2
Bukhara	98,2	106,4	119,8	114,9	117,0	111,8	101,5
Jizzakh	109,7	99,0	129,0	146,9	101,5	116,2	107,0
Kashkadarya	114,4	99,9	110,9	103,2	98,3	117,6	105,3
Navoi	100,3	105,4	147,5	125,6	94,6	116,8	105,5
Namangan	108,6	102,4	123,0	140,8	118,3	109,1	108,5
Samarkand	100,2	95,3	119,6	126,2	111,7	117,8	111,8
Surkhandarya	106,7	107,3	129,7	121,2	109,0	112,9	101,6
Syrdarya	100,2	99,8	149,0	158,2	110,2	109,9	99,7
Tashkent	100,2	100,3	131,1	155,8	107,8	115,3	108,6
Fergana	102,8	95,4	120,4	118,8	115,3	115,3	113,8
Khorezm	101,8	108,2	114,0	119,3	97,4	130,9	101,8
Tashkent city	102,8	120,5	136,5	135,5	106,6	118,3	104,4

The bulk of the construction work on the types of economic activities was created from the construction work carried out on the development of construction projects, the construction of residential and residential buildings and the construction of non-residential buildings. In January 2023, the high volume of new construction works in the cross section of the regions, the city of Tashkent (988.9 billion soum), Tashkent region (357.1 billion soum), Fergana region (250.3 billion soum) and Kashkadarya region (207.3 billion soum) was recorded.

Figure 2. Economic situation in the Republic of Uzbekistan in January-September 2023

In the current forms of statistical observation, since January 1, 2015, in accordance with the “statistical classifier of products (products, work, services) of the Republic of Uzbekistan by type of economic activity (MST)”, the indicator “volume of work carried out on its own by type of activity” is used. The share of construction work performed by large construction organizations in the structure of construction work on the construction of buildings and structures was 7.2%, increasing by 0.1% points compared with the figure for the corresponding period of 2022. In this type of activity, the share corresponding to the contribution of small enterprises and microfirms decreased by 8.0% compared with the corresponding period of 2022, to 59.0%. And the share of the informal sector increased by 7.9% points compared with the corresponding period of 2022 to 33.8%.

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Conclusion

As of February 1, 2023, the total number of enterprises and organizations engaged in construction activities in the Republic of Uzbekistan was 45,591. Also, in January 2023, a total of 426 new construction enterprises were established, with a ratio of 0.9% to operating enterprises. A large part of the construction enterprises, 9,166 or

20.1% of the total enterprises in the Republic, are located in Tashkent. There are also 3,999 construction enterprises in the Tashkent region (8.8% of the total construction enterprises in the Republic) and 3,788 (8.3 %) in the Fergana region, with a larger figure compared to the rest of the regions. From the above indicators, it can be seen that the investment climate in our country is improving, and reforms are showing their effectiveness.

References:

1. Investitsiya va Lizing asoslari – K.Z. Homitov, A.N.Mahmudov
2. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan's decision “on the investment program of the Republic of Uzbekistan 2017”.
3. Address of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Supreme Assembly for 2023.
4. Мухтаров Б. Ozbekiston respublikasida axoli daromadlarini oshish dinamikasi //Современные инновационные исследования актуальные проблемы и развитие тенденции: решения и перспективы. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 579-581.
5. Botir M., Nodirbek X. QO‘SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG‘INING AHOLI DAROMADLARIGA TA’SIRI //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – С. 253-257.
6. Botir M. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TISH DAVRIDA YUZAGA KELAYOTGAN MUAMMOLAR //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – С. 257-260.
7. Mukhtorov B., Ermatov M. METHODS OF EFFECTIVE HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT //International Journal Of Management And Economics Fundamental. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 05. – С. 76-80.
8. Мухтаров Б., Хайруллаев Н. Преимущества и недостатки оффшорных зон //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1.
9. Цой М. П., Эшонкулов Т., Касимова Д. П. Реформы в сфере образования Республики Узбекистан //Гуманитарные науки в XXI веке. – 2014. – №. 18. – С. 210-213.
10. Муртазин Э. Р., Сиддиқов М. Ю., Цой М. П. Стратегия развития экономики Узбекистана-региональные особенности //Региональные проблемы преобразования экономики: интеграционные процессы и механизмы формирования и социально-экономическая политика региона. – 2018. – С. 85-87.
11. Цой М. П., Худояров Р. ЗАКОНОДАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ЦИФРОВОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – С. 37-40.
12. ЦОЙ М. РОЛЬ ГЕНДЕРНОГО РАВЕНСТВА В ВОПРОСАХ СОКРАЩЕНИЯ БЕДНОСТИ И СОЗДАНИЯ ДОСТОЙНЫХ РАБОЧИХ МЕСТ–МИРОВОЙ ОПЫТ И ПРАКТИКА УЗБЕКИСТАНА //Архив научных исследований. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 1.
13. Цой М. П., Худояров Р. Т. МАЛЫЙ И СРЕДНИЙ БИЗНЕС В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ МИРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – С. 132-136.

14. Shahzod M. O‘ZBEKISTONDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI RIVOJLANTIRISH //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – С. 153-156.
15. Mukhtarovich D. K., Mamarajabovich A. K., Schmidt P. Aplikovaná informatika v podnikaní a digitálnom hospodárstve //Economics And Informatics. – 2023. – Т. 21. – №. 1.
16. Khidirnazarov A. PRIORITIES OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES IN THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN //International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 4. – С. 559-561.
17. Xudayarov R., Akhror A. Big data types of education system and opportunities for using them in the field //journal of academic research and trends in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 21-24.
18. To‘ychiyeva N. The main characteristics of innovation management in the higher education system //International conferences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 103-105.
19. Khudoyarov R. Improving economic governance in a market economy //galaxy international interdisciplinary research journal. – 2022. – Т. 10. – №. 2. – С. 610-612.
20. Xudoyorov R. COMPILATION OF FINANCIAL REPORTS BASED ON INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 175-186.
21. Xudayarov R., Akhror A. Big data types of education system and opportunities for using them in the field //journal of academic research and trends in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 21-24.
22. Усмонова В. ХУДУДЛАРДА ИНВЕСТИЦИЯЛАР САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ //Economics and education. – 2022. – Т. 23. – №. 6. – С. 70-74.
23. Усмонова В. Б. ХУДУДЛАР ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА РАҚАМЛИ ИҚТИСОДИЁТ РИВОЖЛАНИШИНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //Current Issues of Bio Economics and Digitalization in the Sustainable Development of Regions (Germany). – 2022. – С. 139-143.
24. Usmanova V. INCREASING INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY //International Journal of Advance Scientific Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 05. – С. 131-138.
25. Azimov Y. THE METHOD OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS BASED ON THE COMPETENCE APPROACH //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 80-91.
26. Yusufjon A. FIZIKA DARSIDA O‘QUVCHILARDA KREATIV FIKRLASHNI RIVOJLANTIRISH //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – С. 368-370.
27. Yusufjon A., Shahzoda U. DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS IN PHYSICS CLASS //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 271-275.
28. АЗИМОВ Ю. ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА КРЕАТИВ ФИКРЛАШНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ВА РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ: АЗИМОВ Юсуфжон, ЎЗМУ Жиззах филиали катта ўқитувчиси //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 7. – С. 302-306.

29. Yusufjon A. DEVELOP CREATIVE THINKING IN STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH //CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 03. – С. 5-8.
30. Рашидов У., Рашидов А. Роль и значение нотариальных методов в регулировании экономики //Вопросы усиления позиций Узбекистана в международной торговле и оптимизации его интеграции в мировой рынок в условиях глобальной трансформации. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 53-58.
31. Abror Ro‘zimumurod o‘g R. et al. RESURSLAR YETISHMAYDIGAN HUDUDNING INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIGINI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING USLUBIY ASOSLARI //O‘ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 290-298.
32. Abror R., Hasanboy K., Husanboy K. GLOBAL IQTISODIY MUAMMOLAR, RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTGA O‘TISHNING AFZALLIKLARI //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – С. 169-175.
33. Abror R., Shahobiddin K. INNOVATIVE MARKETING AND ITS DEVELOPMENT //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – С. 193-196.
34. Rashidov A., Leonodovna M. N., Azlarkhan A. The importance of financial accounting in business decision-making //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2023. – Т. 21. – С. 1-4.
35. Raipovna V. S., Akramovich N. A., Sevinch K. PRODUCTION CAPACITY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES AND WAYS TO INCREASE IT //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 238-241.
36. Xolmuradovich X. B. et al. THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SPORTS SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN, THE GUARANTEE OF THE HEALTHY AND WELL-ROUNDED YOUTH //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 266-269.
37. Akramovich N. A. et al. IMPACT OF HIDDEN ECONOMY ON SOCIETY IN UZBEKISTAN, WAYS TO REDUCE IT //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 142-147.
38. Xolmuradovich X. B. et al. GOVERNMENT AND NON-GOVERNMENT FORMS OF BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP SUPPORT //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 258-265.
39. Худояров Р., Низаметдинов А. МАЛЫЙ И СРЕДНИЙ БИЗНЕС В УСЛОВИЯХ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ МИРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ //Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6 Part 2. – С. 188-193.
40. Норбеков Х., Туйчиева Н. Формирование конкурентных преимуществ компании //Современные инновационные исследования актуальные проблемы и развитие тенденции: решения и перспективы. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 589-592.
41. Норбеков Х. Методики анализа и оценка взаимный преимуществ предприятия //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2022.
42. Норбеков Х. РАЗВИТИЕ ТУРИСТИЧЕСКОЙ СФЕРЫ В МИРЕ И В ОТДЕЛЬНЫХ РЕГИОНАХ //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – С. 141-144.

43. Norbekov X. Формирование конкурентных преимуществ АО «Тандер» //Scienceweb academic papers collection. – 2022.
44. Bahrom X. et al. O'ZBEKISTON VA AQSHNING IQTISODIY MUNOSABATLARI //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – C. 63-69.
45. Sarvar G., Sirojiddin S. Pulatova Mashhura Xushnodbek qizi.(2022). Factors affecting labor relations and its wage //Journal of academic research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – T. 1. – №. 12. – C. 125-129.
46. Akramovich N. A., Sarvar G., Yassim H. THE PLACE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY TODAY //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 12. – C. 95-99.
47. G'aybullayev S. The place of the digital economy today //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 116-126.
48. G'Aybullayev Sarvar O. et al. O 'zbekistonda iste'mol savatchasi hozirgi holatini va uni shakillantirish yo 'nalishlari //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 119-125.
49. Baxrom X., Alijon N., Aziz Z. THE ROLE OF THE PRIVATE SECTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 12. – C. 130-136.
50. Xaydarov, B., & Saitov, S. (2022). Raqamli iqtisodiyot tushunchasi va afzalliklari. Zamonaviy Innovatsion Tadqiqotlarning Dolzarb Muammolari Va Rivojlanish Tendensiyalari: Yechimlar Va Istiqbollar, 1(1), 634–635. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/zitdmrt/article/view/5390>
51. Bahrom X. et al. O'ZBEKISTON VA AQSHNING IQTISODIY MUNOSABATLARI //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – C. 63-69.
52. Xolmuradovich X. B. RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTDA BUXGALTERIYA VA AUDITNI O'RNI //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – C. 128-131.
53. Sirojiddin S., Azizbek A. TRANSITION TO THE MARKET ECONOMY AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS IN UZBEKISTAN //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 11. – C. 255-258.
54. O'G'Li N. D. R., Qizi T. D. Z. MOLIYA BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA UNGA OID YANGI YONDASHUVLAR //Journal of marketing, business and management. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 8. – C. 1-4.
55. Najmiddinov D. R., Shodlikov D. E. THE EFFECT OF THE SECRET ECONOMY IN A DAILY LIFE OF THE SOCIETY //Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1A. – C. 56-59.
56. Dilshod N. XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA KORXONALARDA TUSHUMLAR AUDITINI TASHKIL QILISH BOSQICHLARI VA DASTAKLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2022. – C. 105-110.
57. Uchkun S., Dilshod N. PROCESS OF IDENTIFYING THE SIGNIFICANT ACCOUNTS IN THE REVENUE CYCLE //Journal of marketing, business and management. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 32-36.

58. Нажмиддинов Д., Абдурахимов М. Yashirin iqtisodiyotning jamiyatga ta'siri //Современные тенденции инновационного развития науки и образования в глобальном мире. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 193-196.
59. Alijon N., Sirojiddin S., Azizbek A. FRANCHISE SYSTEM IN BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 250-257.
60. Sarvar G. et al. FACTORS AFFECTING LABOR RELATIONS AND ITS WAGE //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 125-129.
61. Sirojiddin S. et al. SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IS A PLACE TO PROVIDE EMPLOYMENT //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 115-119.
62. Сайтов С., Хонкелов Я. Raqamli iqtisodiyotning bugungi kundagi o'rni //Новый Узбекистан: успешный международный опыт внедрения международных стандартов финансовой отчетности. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 301-304.
63. Sirojiddin S. et al. PRICE AND ITS ROLE IN ENSURING THE STABILITY OF PRODUCTS AND RAW MATERIALS IN SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN //Journal of Academic Research and Trends in Educational Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 12. – С. 357-365.
64. Соловарова М. А. ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СЕТИ ОТЕЛЕЙ MARRIOTT //Казанский вестник молодых учёных. – 2022. – Т. 6. – №. 3. – С. 98-103.
65. Norkuziyev A. R. Theoretical Analysis Of Role Infrastructure On The Development Smes In Uzbekistan //International Conference Dedicated To The Role And Importance Of Innovative Education In The 21st Century. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 9. – С. 131-135.
66. Rustamovich N. A. O 'ZBEKISTON HUDUDLARIDA ICHKI RESURSLARGA ASOSLANGAN HUDUDIY INFRATUZILMASIDAN FOYDALANISH IMKOMIYATLARI VA MAMLAKATIMIZDA INNAVATSION USULDA FOYDALANISH //O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 17. – С. 104-115.
67. Наркузиёв А. Р. ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ПОНЯТИЯ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЫ КАК ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ КАТЕГОРИИ И ЕЕ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ В СФЕРЕ ПРОИЗВОДСТВА //PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 21. – С. 11-14.
68. Rustamovich N. A. ROLE OF INFRASTRUCTURE TO DEVELOP SMALL BUSINESS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – Т. 9. – С. 412-416.
69. Narkuziyev A. R. ICHKI RESURSLARGA ASOSLANGAN HUDUDIY INFRATUZILMANI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASINI QO 'LLASH (O 'ZBEKISTONDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK SOHASI UCHUN FOYDALANISH IMKOMIYATLARI) //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. TSTU Conference 2. – С. 390-400.
70. Kamolov D. Davlat boshqaruviga oid axloqiy qarashlar //Адабиёт учкунлари. – 2021.
71. Kamolov D. R. O. G. L. O'ZBEKISTONDA DEMOKRATIYA VA AXLOQNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI //Academic research in educational sciences.

– 2022. – Т. 3. – №. NUU Conference 2. – С. 348-352.

72. Kamolov Dostonbek, “SPIRITUAL AND MORAL ENVIRONMENT OF SOCIETY”, SSAI, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 128–133, Oct. 2023, Accessed: Oct. 24, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/ssai/article/view/89>

73. O‘G‘LI K. D. R. ON THE WAY TO THE DIGITAL EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN //“O‘zbekiston Milliy universitetining ilm-fan rivoji va jamiyat taraqqiyotida tutgan o‘rni” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya. – 2023.

74. O‘G‘LI K. D. R. O‘zbekiston raqamli ta‘lim tizimi yo‘lida //“O‘zbekiston Milliy universitetining ilm-fan rivoji va jamiyat taraqqiyotida tutgan o‘rni” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya. – 2023.

75. Усмонова В. ХУДУДЛАРДА ИНВЕСТИЦИЯЛАР САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШ //Economics and education.– 2022. – Т. 23. – №. 6. – С. 70-74.

76. Цой М., Холмирзаев Н., Иброхимов Ш. ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКИЙ КАПИТАЛ И ТЕНДЕНЦИИ ЕГО РАЗВИТИЯ //“ Milliy iqtisodiyotni isloh qilish va barqaror rivojlantirish istiqbollari” respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallari to‘plami. – 2023. – С. 305-308.

77. Цой М. П., Холмирзаев Н., Иброхимов Ш. ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОЙ СРЕДЫ КАК ЭЛЕМЕНТ РЕАЛИЗАЦИИ КОНСТИТУЦИОННОГО ПРАВА НА ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ //International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research. – 2023. – С. 33-37.

78. Цой М. П., Разногорская М. Я. ПОДГОТОВКА ПЕДАГОГОВ-ПСИХОЛОГОВ И ИХ КОММУНИКАТИВНАЯ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТЬ //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 22. – №. 2. – С. 97-101.

79. Ботировна, У. В. (2022). ХУДУДЛАР ТАРАҚҚИЁТИДА РАҚАМЛИ ИҚТИСОДИЁТ РИВОЖЛАНИШИНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.

80. Kamolov D. R. O. G. L. O‘ZBEKISTONDA DEMOKRATIYA VA AXLOQNING ZAMONAVIY MUAMMOLARI VA YECHIMLARI //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. NUU Conference 2. – С. 348-352.

81. Kamolov Dostonbek, “SPIRITUAL AND MORAL ENVIRONMENT OF SOCIETY”, SSAI, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 128–133, Oct. 2023, Accessed: Oct. 24, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://supportresult.uz/index.php/ssai/article/view/89>

82. O‘G‘LI K. D. R. ON THE WAY TO THE DIGITAL EDUCATION SYSTEM OF UZBEKISTAN //“O‘zbekiston Milliy universitetining ilm-fan rivoji va jamiyat taraqqiyotida tutgan o‘rni” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya. – 2023.

83. O‘G‘LI K. D. R. O‘zbekiston raqamli ta‘lim tizimi yo‘lida //“O‘zbekiston Milliy universitetining ilm-fan rivoji va jamiyat taraqqiyotida tutgan o‘rni” mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya. – 2023.

84. Kamolov D. Davlat boshqaruviga oid axloqiy qarashlar //Адабиёт учкунлари. – 2021.

85. Usmanova V. INCREASING INVESTMENT ATTRACTIVENESS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY //International Journal of Advance Scientific Research. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 05. – С. 131-138.